

WHAT IF MATHS IS TAUGHT TO OLDER PUPILS THROUGH MATHEMATICAL STORY PICTURE BOOKS?

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Learning mathematics through reading and creating mathematical story picture books can be a powerful pedagogical strategy for older primary school pupils, but first, what are mathematical story picture books?

KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF MATHEMATICAL STORY PICTURE BOOKS

Just like any story picture books, mathematical story picture books (MSPB) also have a plot, a cast of characters and page illustrations. What makes MSPB unique is that mathematical concepts are either explicitly or implicitly woven into the plot to either demonstrate the concept or show how the concept can be used by characters to solve a problem found in the story.

Take, for example, ‘Fractions in Disguise’ (Einhorn, 2014). This story is about George Cornelius Factor (GCF) who invents a machine called ‘Reducer’ to help him find a very sought-after fraction ($\frac{5}{9}$) that has been stolen from a fraction auction and has been disguised as another fraction by the villainous Dr. Brok. While at Dr. Brok’s mansion, GCF uses his knowledge of equivalent fractions (in the form of the Reducer machine) to reveal the true form of a range of fractions (e.g. $\frac{3}{21}$ is really $\frac{1}{7}$; $\frac{34}{63}$ is already in its true form; $\frac{8}{10}$ is really $\frac{4}{5}$, and so on). Finally, GCF comes across $\frac{35}{63}$ which is later revealed as the $\frac{5}{9}$ fraction he has been looking for.

When we examine the above story structurally, we will see that mathematical knowledge (i.e. knowledge of equivalent fractions) is required to help the character solve the problem. The page illustrations also help readers visually see how $\frac{35}{63}$ is in fact the same as $\frac{5}{9}$. In brief, MTSB are a specific genre of literature, and they are not (and should never be) mathematics textbooks or worksheets in disguise.

Moreover, as the above story shows, MSPB are more than just counting books. There are several MSPB that focus on mathematics concepts for upper Key Stage 2 pupils (9-11 year olds), such as any titles in the Sir Cumference series. Furthermore, there are also several MSPB with a focus on mathematical concepts for Key Stages 3 and 4 (12-14 year olds), such as ‘What's Your Angle, Pythagoras?’ (Ellis, 2014) for Pythagoras' theorem, and ‘Anno's Magic Seeds’ (Anno, 1999) for exponential growth, among several others.

WHY SHOULD WE TEACH MATHEMATICS TO OLDER PUPILS USING STORY PICTURE BOOKS?

The idea of using MSPB to enrich mathematics learning is not a new idea. In fact, it has been around for almost three decades, particularly in the early years setting. What is less common, particularly in the UK, is using MSPB to enrich mathematics learning beyond the early years level. I have been arguing - and will continue to argue - that the approach could also benefit mathematics learning of older pupils. Specifically, I would argue that the use of MSPB could:

foster pupils' conceptual understanding through multi-representation of mathematical concepts and variation of mathematical situations; develop language skills; and foster engagement with mathematics learning.

Foster conceptual understanding through multi-representation

We can all (hopefully) agree that we do not teach mathematics so that our pupils become a human calculator, that is someone who is good at churning out correct mathematical answers but without conceptually understanding the concept behind it.

As part of one of my research projects, when Jack (pseudonym), a 9-year-old pupil, was asked by me what $20 \div 5$ equals, he was able to give me the correct answer (4) almost instantly. Then, when he was asked to (contextually) represent $20 \div 5$ using a word problem, this is what he came up with: "Spanish Yoda had a can of Coke and a bag of bananas and apples and paint. How much did it cost her? Coke: £1.00. Bag of bananas: £2.00. Apples: £8.00. Paint: £9.00. Total £20.00". How Jack's word problem is related to $20 \div 5$ remains a mystery.

What Jack demonstrates here is a classic example of pupils whose procedural fluency (i.e. the mechanic aspect of mathematical learning) in relation to division is good, but have yet to fully grasp what the concept means conceptually.

As many mathematics education scholars have argued, in order to demonstrate conceptual understanding in mathematics, pupils must be able to represent mathematical concepts in different ways using different representations (e.g. contextualisation, visualisation, etc.). Here, I would argue that key features of MSPB, such as narrative and page illustrations, make learning mathematics conceptually effective as pupils get to learn mathematical concepts through these different representations.

Foster conceptual understanding through variation

Another key strength of teaching mathematics using MSPB is the development of pupils' conceptual understanding in mathematics through what I refer to as the variation of mathematical situations that are often found in well-written MSPB. To explain this concept, take 'Bean Thirteen' (McElligott, 2007) as an example. The story follows two crickets, Ralph and Flora, who have collected twelve beans to bring home for dinner. When Flora decides to pick one more bean (i.e. Bean Thirteen), Ralph is convinced it will bring bad luck. No matter how many friends they invite to try to share the 13 beans equally, it is always impossible.

Situation 1: 13 beans to be shared between 2 crickets (Ralph and Flora) resulting in 1 remaining bean (6 beans each)

Situation 2: 13 beans to be shared between 3 crickets (Ralph, Flora and 1 friend) resulting in 1 remaining bean (4 beans each)

Situation 3: 13 beans to be shared between 4 crickets (Ralph, Flora and 2 friends) resulting in 1 remaining bean (3 beans each)

Situation 4: 13 beans to be shared between 5 crickets (Ralph, Flora and 3 friends) resulting in 3 remaining beans (2 beans each)

Situation 5: 13 beans to be shared between 6 crickets (Ralph, Flora and 4 friends) resulting in 1 remaining bean (2 beans each)

In this example, while the number of crickets varies, the number of beans is invariant. Through this variation of mathematical situations, rich mathematical investigations are made possible. Pupils can be asked, for example, to continue the pattern to prove that 13 cannot be divided evenly by any other numbers except for 13 itself (and hence demonstrating the meaning of prime numbers in the process). I argue that such variation of mathematical situations is crucial to foster pupils' conceptual understanding in mathematics.

Develop language skills

From my earlier research (Trakulphadetkrai, Courtney, Clenton, Treffers-Daller, & Tsakalaki, 2017) and those of others, it has been found that children's mathematical abilities are linked to their language abilities. What is exciting is how recent research (e.g. Hassinger-Das, Jordan, & Dyson, 2015; Purpura, Napoli, Wehrspann, & Gold, 2017) has also found the positive impact of using stories when teaching mathematics concepts to young children on the development of their language abilities particularly their vocabulary knowledge. Why not kill two birds with one stone? Why not teach mathematics using MSPB to develop both pupils' mathematical and language development at the same time?

Engagement through emotional investment

Another key advantage of teaching mathematics using MSPB is that pupils arguably do not see MSPB in the same way that they see, for example, mathematics textbooks or worksheets with word problems after word problems to be solved. They are more likely to view MSPB as something that they can be emotionally invested in, and something that they can enjoy interacting with over and over again either together with the whole class or in their own time at their own pace. Research (e.g. McAndrew, Morris, & Fennell, 2017) has recently found that the use of stories in mathematics teaching can help to foster children's positive attitude towards the subject.

HOW TO USE STORY PICTURE BOOKS IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS?

Reading a mathematical story at the start of a mathematics lesson can help to engage pupils. This also sets the scene and contextualises the mathematics to be taught. Other teachers prefer to wait until the end of the lesson to read the story, to consolidate the learning of mathematics.

Alternatively, teachers might not want to finish reading their chosen story in one go. Quite often, there is a problem for the characters in the story to solve using their mathematical knowledge. Teachers could stop reading the story just before a solution is revealed and use the story's plot to encourage pupils to solve the problem themselves through mathematical investigations.

The beauty of teaching mathematics using MSPB lies in its flexibility: there is not one specific way of integrating MSPB in mathematics teaching. Teachers can be as creative as they like.

WHAT IF PUPILS CREATE THEIR OWN MATHEMATICAL STORY PICTURE BOOKS?

Beyond reading MSPB to pupils, a more innovative mathematics learning strategy that I have been trying to highlight to mathematics teachers (and curriculum developers) in the UK and

abroad is the idea of getting pupils to develop their mathematical understanding through creating their own MSPB.

Here, I am not talking about asking pupils to create a full-feature 30-page MSPB. As a mathematics learning activity, pupils can simply be asked to create their own mini MSPB with just 10 pages whereby, for example, the first 2 pages set the scene and the problem to be solved by the characters; the next 6 pages can feature three variations (or attempts) in which the characters try to use their mathematical knowledge to solve the problem; and the story can come to a close on the last two pages.

With this activity, pupils need to think carefully about the storyline, which requires them to consider practical and meaningful applications of the mathematical concept in question. In brief, they need to contextualise abstract mathematical concepts. Additionally, as the focus is on presenting the stories in picture book format, pupils also need to actively think about page illustrations, and how best to communicate abstract mathematical concepts and situations visually to their readers. As previously highlighted, not only could learning mathematics through storytelling benefit pupils mathematically, it could also develop their language and creative writing skills and make possible a great cross-curricular teaching and learning opportunity. Equally important, the approach would allow pupils to see mathematics in a different light – one that is less test-driven, and more fun and imaginative. This is crucial especially if we want to improve pupils' perceptions of the subject.

The preliminary findings of my pilot research with Year 4 pupils on the effectiveness of this mathematics learning activity is promising. Specifically, the results indicate that pupils in the intervention class (i.e. those that were asked to create MSPB on multiplication over the period of a week) had better conceptual understanding of multiplication (as measured through the study's test) than their peers in the comparison class who learned multiplication the normal way (e.g. worksheets and textbooks, etc.).

From a distance, having pupils create their own MSPB might look like a cute, fun activity. However, when one carefully examines this approach, one will see just how pedagogically powerful it can be. I am surprised this approach has not been used more often, because it costs nothing in terms of resources – just a few sheets of A4 paper, a pencil and a splash of imagination!

This mathematics learning activity can also save teachers' time. For example, if the concept in focus is multiplication, teachers could start the day with their mathematics lesson by getting their pupils to consider everyday situations where having knowledge about multiplication can help solve problems, and how the concept can be represented visually. Later in the literacy lesson, they could get their pupils to come up with the plot, characters and setting. They could also get them to work on their draft writing paying attention to things like grammar. After lunch, in an art lesson, the pupils could work on page illustrations, and putting their MSPB together. Before home time, the pupils could read their MSPB with the help of a visualiser to their peers. This one activity can be meaningfully integrated across different curricular subjects throughout the day. What's more – teachers would have just one set of work to mark.

MATHSTHROUGHSTORIES.ORG

Drawing from key findings of my other research project which set out to explore teachers' perceived barriers on the integration of storytelling in mathematics teaching (e.g. Farrugia, & Trakulphadetkrai, In preparation; Markovits, Chen-Haddad, & Trakulphadetkrai, In preparation; Prendergast, Harbison, Miller, & Trakulphadetkrai, 2018; Yang, Su, Chen, & Trakulphadetkrai, In preparation), I designed and created my non-profit research project's website called MathsThroughStories.org.

The website contains the world's largest database of recommendations for MSPB (500+), reviews of MSPB, MSPB-based lesson ideas, exclusive interviews with MSPB authors, and a list of relevant research studies done on the topic, among several other free resources. Since the launch of the website in Spring 2017, the website has now been visited over 300,000 times by more than 60,000 teachers and parents from over 180 countries.

MathsThroughStories.org also organises the Young Mathematical Story Author (YMSA) competition, an annual international competition set up to encourage young mathematics learners (8-13 years old) from around the world to embed their mathematics learning in a meaningful and engaging context through creating their own MSPB. I hope anyone – be it teachers, academics, policy makers or even parents – who is interested in this topic will find this website useful.

FINAL WORDS

Teaching mathematics using MSPB should not only be found in Nursery and Reception classes. This creative, cross-curricular and research-informed mathematics teaching and learning approach should too be utilised by teachers teaching a primary school class (particularly those at the upper Key Stage 2 level). With that in mind, more research on this pedagogical approach for older primary school pupils is desperately needed.

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